

ROLE OF POTENTIAL CLINICAL PHARMACIST IN THE MANAGEMENT OF TYPE-2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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ABSTRACT

Background Type-2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) begins more moderately, as shortage of insulin is caused by an imbalance in insulin levels and response. The most prevalent causes of resistance to insulin are aging and obesity. By considering HbA1c, this study investigates the effects of potential clinical pharmacist (intern student) intervention on diabetic management among patients undergoing counselling and the control group. **Methods** A prospective longitudinal study was conducted among adults (≥ 18 years) with T2DM between August, 2024 and January, 2025. Participants who provided informed consent with T2DM were included, while those with type 1 diabetes, gestational diabetes, or severe organ dysfunction were excluded. **Results** The study found that over six months, the potential clinical pharmacist approach greatly enhanced glucose control in patients with T2DM ($p < .001$). Compared to patients who underwent pharmacist counselling

showed a greater decrease in their HbA1c values ($p < .001$) when compared to no intervention (control) group. Further, medication adherence and KAP scores increased considerably among counseled patients. Compared to patients in control group, those in intervention group saw a greater decrease in their HbA1c values ($p < .001$).

Conclusion: The study demonstrated that a potential clinical pharmacist (Pharm D intern) led

educational intervention significantly enhanced participants' diabetes self-management. These findings highlight the effectiveness of patient education in improving diabetes awareness and care, supporting the integration of such interventions to optimize patient outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Clinical pharmacist, Patient counselling, glycemic control, intervention, HbA1c, KAP.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder caused by impaired insulin secretion or action, resulting in persistent hyperglycemia and multisystem complications. It includes type 1, type 2, gestational, neonatal diabetes, and maturity-onset diabetes of the young, with type 1 and type 2 being the most prevalent. Type 1 diabetes results from autoimmune destruction of pancreatic beta cells, whereas type 2 diabetes is mainly associated with insulin resistance influenced by age, obesity, and lifestyle factors. The global burden of diabetes has increased markedly, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Clinical pharmacists play a crucial role in optimizing medication therapy, improving adherence, and enhancing patient outcomes through collaborative diabetes care.^[1,2] The main objective of this study was to estimate the effect of potential clinical pharmacists' (Pharm D Interns) role in enhancing glycemic management by measuring HbA1c.

METHODS

Study Design

A prospective longitudinal interventional study.

Target Study Population and Study Time

- The target study population were people aged ≥ 18 years with T2DM.
- The study was conducted between August, 2024 and January, 2025.

Inclusion & Exclusion criteria Inclusion Criteria

- Patients Aged ≥ 18 yr
- Individuals diagnosed with T2DM
- Those agreeing to participate in the study and sign ICF

Exclusion criteria

- Patients with T1DM.

- Patients with gestational diabetes.
- Individuals who have severe organ damage.

Recruitment of the Study Population

The study population were recruited through convenient sampling of T2DM patients from OPD (outpatient department) of a private teaching hospital.

Sample Size Calculation

Sample size calculation was done using online sample size calculator with 50% response distribution, 5% margin of error, and 95% CI. The estimated sample size was 75 for control group and 75 for the intervention group.

Development of Case Collection Form

The case collection form was designed containing six sections. Section-A was designed to collect the patient's socio-demographic data like age, gender, height, weight, history of complications, laboratory data (HbA1C) etc. Section B consisted of 12 questions related to knowledge regarding T2DM. The questionnaire was adapted.^[3,4,5] and modified to suit our objectives. Section-C contained five statements to evaluate the patient's attitude toward the disease on a 5-point Likert scale. Section-D contained five questions regarding their practices. Section-E contained eight questions to check the medication adherence of the patient's using a 5-point Likert scale and Section-F contained six questions to evaluate the patient's satisfaction with intervention (patient counselling) using a 5-point Likert scale.^[6]

Validation of case collection form

The case collection form was validated by two pharmacology and three pharmacy practice experts. It was examined to ensure that it shows completeness, clarity, and alignment with the studies objectives. The authors considered the recommendations and enhanced the CCF by integrating their input. Further, the CCF was subjected to a reliability test using Cronbach's alpha coefficient and was found to be $\alpha=0.80$ and was found to have good reliability (Kaliyaperumal K.2004).^[7]

Ethical clearance

The proposal, along with the case collection form and ICF, was submitted to Institutional Review Boards (GCP-IRB) for approval and ethical clearance was obtained (vide ref. GCPK/PD24/13; Dated: 27/08/2024) and Informed Consent Form (ICF) were signed and

collected from all participants before initiation of the study.

Statistical Analysis

The survey data was tabulated using Microsoft Excel and analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences -SPSS version - 25 (IBM SPSS Statistical software) for windows. The demographic characteristics (categorical variables) of the participants were illustrated using descriptive statistics for frequency, percentage, mean (SD) or median (IQR). The categorical variables were analysed using frequency and percentage distribution and p-value computed using Pearson's Chi Square test. A p value < .05 was considered significant. The reliability, internal consistency and corrected item-total correlations were assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient and the knowledge, attitude and practice scores were calculated.

Assuming that the data are normally distributed, a normality test using Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) and Shapiro-Wilk was run. Since significance values were < .05, non-parametric test was chosen. The data were analysed using Friedman test as a non-parametric one-way analysis for repeated measures. A post hoc pair-wise application of the Wilcoxon signed rank test with Bonferroni corrected levels of observed significance was used to locate precise differences (Green & Salkind, 2008).^[8]

RESULTS

Response Rate

A total of 180 patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) were enrolled from the private teaching hospital for the study. Of these, only 175 valid samples were retrieved (response rate: 97%). The participants in the pilot study were excluded from the final analysis. The primary reason for study drop outs were participants' inability to attend the scheduled survey.

Distribution of data

Normality assessment using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed that all study variables were not-normally distributed ($p < 0.05$). Hence, non-parametric statistical tests were employed, and the null hypothesis was rejected.

Sociodemographic Data

A total of 175 participants were divided into two groups, the intervention group: $n = 86$; and control group: $n = 89$). Most participants were aged 40–60 years. Median age was lower in the intervention group [54.5 years (IQR 16)] compared to the control group [59 years (IQR 18)].

Mean duration of diabetes was longer in the intervention group (5.9 ± 4.74 years) than in the control group (5.09 ± 3.38 years). Family history of diabetes was reported by 15% of intervention participants and 11% of control. Non-smokers constituted the majority of the study population, accounting for 87% of the intervention group and 83% of the control group. Abstinence from alcohol was reported by 66% in both the intervention and control groups. A history of diabetic complications was reported by approximately 60–65% of participants in the control group, compared to only 20–25% in the intervention group. This marked difference indicates a lower complication burden among patients receiving interventions. Most of the participants were of mixed diet accounting to about 91% and 97% in intervention and control group respectively (Table No.1).

Study outcomes at two different timelines

The study results indicate that the structured intervention had a statistically significant and positive impact on both clinical and behavioural outcomes. The intervention group demonstrated a significant reduction in mean HbA1c levels at follow-up ($p < 0.001$), reflecting improved glycaemic control. Additionally, there was a marked shift from poor and average to good categories in KAP scores and medication adherence ($p < 0.001$), indicating enhanced patient knowledge, self-care practices, and treatment compliance. In contrast, the control group showed minimal or statistically insignificant improvements in most parameters. Overall, the findings confirm that the intervention was effective in improving glycaemic outcomes and promoting better disease management behaviours among participants (Table No.2).

History of Diabetic Complications

A history of diabetic complications was reported by only 3% of participants in the control group, when compared to 23% in the intervention group. This marked difference in complication burden among patients receiving intervention (Fig. 1).

Past Medical History

Hypertension was the predominant comorbidity in both the intervention (40%) and control (34%) groups respectively. Coronary artery disease and cerebrovascular accident were observed in small proportions in both groups. Other conditions such as cardiovascular disease, sinusitis, and thyroid disorders were only reported in the intervention group. Overall, the intervention group showed a slightly higher prevalence and wider spectrum of comorbidities compared to the control group (Fig. 2).

Anti-diabetic drugs Prescribed

Metformin 500 mg was the most frequently prescribed anti-diabetic drug in both the intervention (34%) and control (25%) groups. Sitagliptin-based combination therapy was more common in the control group, while combinations with Glimepiride and Voglibose were used in both groups. Monotherapy agents such as Dapagliflozin, Voglibose, and Teneligliptin were more frequently prescribed in the intervention group. Overall, the intervention group demonstrated greater use of Metformin monotherapy and varied combinations, whereas the control group favoured Sitagliptin-based combinations (Fig. 3).

Anti-hypertensive drugs Prescribed

Hypertension was the most prevalent comorbidity in both the intervention (40%) and control (34%) groups. ARBs like telmisartan were most commonly prescribed whereas CCBs were comparatively less prescribed (Fig. 4).

Cardioprotective drugs Prescribed

Atorvastatin 20 mg was the most frequently prescribed cardioprotective drug in the intervention group, followed by Clopidogrel and Ecospirin whereas, in the control group, Ecosprin 75 mg was the only commonly prescribed agent. Other statins and aspirin combinations were used exclusively in the intervention group. Overall, the intervention group demonstrated greater utilization and a broader range of cardioprotective medications compared to the control group (Fig. 5).

Association between Knowledge scores and Sociodemographic variables

At baseline, knowledge levels in the intervention group varied significantly across BMI ($p=0.01$), diet pattern ($p=0.001$), and family history of diabetes mellitus ($p=0.001$), indicating the influence of these demographic factors prior to educational intervention. After the intervention, a shift toward good knowledge was observed across most subgroups, and post-intervention associations with BMI ($p=0.46$), diet ($p=0.81$), occupation ($p=0.95$), smoking history ($p=0.18$), alcohol history ($p=0.56$), and family history ($p=0.41$) were no longer statistically significant.

In the control group, baseline knowledge scores were not significantly associated with age, gender, BMI, diet, smoking, alcohol consumption, or family history. However, occupation remained significantly associated with knowledge levels during both test ($p=0.007$) and re-test ($p=0.02$).

Overall, the intervention group showed marked improvement in knowledge with reduced demographic influence, whereas the control group demonstrated minimal change, with knowledge variability continuing to be influenced by occupation (Table No.3).

Association between Attitude score and Sociodemographic variables

At baseline, attitude scores in the intervention group were significantly associated with BMI ($p=0.005$) and family history of diabetes mellitus ($p=0.009$), indicating the influence of physical status and hereditary risk on participants' attitudes toward disease management. Following the intervention, smoking history showed a statistically significant improvement ($p=0.005$), while previously significant associations with BMI and family history became non-significant in the re-test, suggesting improved uniformity in attitude across subgroups.

Other variables such as age, gender, diet, occupation, and alcohol consumption remained non-significant throughout the test and re-test periods. In the control group, no statistically significant changes in attitude were observed across most demographic variables between test and re-test, and minor variations noted in diet and family history which were not statistically significant.

Overall, the intervention group demonstrated a positive shift in attitude over time, whereas the control group showed minimal change, highlighting the effectiveness of the intervention in improving participants' attitudes (Table No.4).

Association Between Sociodemographic Variables and Practice Scores

Practice-based responses in the intervention group showed no significant associations with demographic variables during baseline testing. However, following intervention, participants demonstrated improvements in healthy practices regardless of age, gender, BMI, diet, occupation, smoking or alcohol status. This indicates that the intervention had a uniform impact on translating knowledge and attitude into practice, overcoming demographic barriers that may influence behavioural change.

In the control group, significant associations were observed with gender ($p=0.02$) and smoking history ($p=0.02$) during baseline assessment. Although these associations were no longer significant during re-test, improvements in practice levels remained minimal.

The intervention group demonstrated marked improvement in practice scores between test and re-test, reflecting effective adoption of recommended health behaviours. Conversely, the

control group exhibited only slight, statistically insignificant changes, indicating poor behavioral transition in the absence of intervention (Table No.5).

Satisfaction Score

The mean satisfaction score for the intervention group was found to be 25.64 ± 1.18 out of 30. The intervention group effectively responded to patient counselling from a potential clinical pharmacist, as evidenced by the high mean score.

FIGURES

History of Diabetic Complications

Figure 1: Diabetic Complications among the study Participants.

Figure 2: Past Medical History.

Figure 3: Anti-diabetic drugs Prescribed.

Figure 4: Anti-hypertensive drugs Prescribed.

Figure 5: Cardioprotective drugs Prescribed.

Table No.1: Socio Demographic data of Intervention and Control Group.

Variables	Intervention (N=86) N (%)	Control (N=89) N (%)
Age in Years [Median (IQR)]	54.5 (IQR 16)	59 (IQR 18)
Below 40years	10 (12)	5 (6)
40 - 60years	51 (59)	43 (48)
Above 60years	25 (29)	41 (46)
Gender		
Male	49 (57)	44 (49)
Female	37 (43)	45 (51)
Duration of diabetes in years [Median (IQR)]	5.9 ± 4.74	5.09 ±3.38
Below 5 years	54 (63)	63 (71)
5 - 10 years	25 (29)	21 (24)
11 - 20 years	7 (8)	5 (5)
Family history of DM		
Positive	13 (15)	10 (11)
Negative	73 (85)	79 (89)
Occupation		
Unemployed	29 (34)	27(30)
Self employed	47(54)	58(65)
Employed	10(12)	4(5)
BMI [Median (IQR)]	25.55 (IQR 4.21)	25.91 (IQR 3.46)
Under weight	1 (1)	0(0)
Ideal weight	30(37)	31(35)
Overweight	43(53)	52(59)
Obese	7(9)	5(6)
Smoking History		
No	75(87)	74(83)
Yes	11(13)	15(17)
Alcohol History		
No	57(66)	59(66)
Yes	29(34)	30(34)
Diet		
Veg	8(9)	3(3)
Non-veg	0(0)	0(0)
Mixed diet	78(91)	86(97)

Table No. 2: Study outcomes at two different timelines.

Variables	Intervention	Control
HbA1C-1 (Test)		
Mean	8.05	7.38
SD	2.04	1.02
P value	<0.001*	.075
HbA1C-2 (Re-test)		
Mean	7.56	7.46
SD	1.85	1.02
P value	<0.001*	.097
KAP Score-1 (Test)		

Poor	29	17
Average	30	48
Good	27	24
P value	.92	<0.001*
KAP Score-2 (Re-test)		
Poor	3	16
Average	6	43
Good	77	30
P value	<0.001*	.002
Medication Adherence Scale-1 (Test)		
Poor	32	32
Average	22	17
Good	32	40
P value	.313	.010
Medication Adherence Scale-2 (Re-test)		
Poor	7	27
Average	23	24
Good	56	38
P value	<0.001*	.160
*Chi Square Test, p < .05 is significant.		

Table No. 3: Test-Retest Comparison of Knowledge Scores of Study Participants at Two Time Points.

Variables	Intervention Group (N = 86)								Control Group (N = 84)									
	(%)	Test (response in %)				Re-test (response in %)				(%)	Test (response in %)				Re-test (response in %)			
		Pr	Av	Gd	P	Pr	Av	Gd	P		Pr	Av	Gd	P	Pr	Av	Gd	P
Age																		
<40 yrs	12	13	11	0	.81	0	12	11	.94	6	4	5	50	.08	0	6	50	.06
40-60 yrs	59	61	57	100		50	58	63		48	44	50	50		56	46	50	
>60 yrs	29	26	31	0		50	30	26		46	52	45	0		44	48	0	
Gender																		
Male	57	52	59	50	.84	0	60	56	.24	49	48	50	50	.99	44	51	50	.88
Female	43	48	41	50		100	40	44		51	52	50	50		56	49	50	
BMI																		
Under weight	1	0	2	0	.01*	0	2	0	.46	0	0	0	0	.19	0	0	0	.07
Ideal weight	37	5	47	0		0	31	52		35	22	39	0		13	39	100	
Over weight	53	82	44	100		100	56	44		59	70	56	100		74	57	0	
Obese	9	14	7	0		0	11	4		6	7	5	0		13	4	0	
Diet																		
Veg	9	0	10	100	.001*	0	11	7	.81	3	0	5	0	.47	0	4	0	.67
Non-Veg	0	0	0	0		0	0	0		0	0	0	0		0	0	0	
Mixed Diet	91	100	90	0		100	89	93		97	100	95	100		100	96	100	
Occupation																		
Un employed	34	0	33	39	.48	50	35	30	.95	30	0	25	44	.007*	44	28	0	.02*
Self employed	54	100	52	57		50	53	59		65	50	70	56		56	68	50	
Employed	12	0	15	4		0	12	11		5	50	5	0		0	4	50	
Smoking history																		
Yes	87	78	90	100	.29	100	82	96	.18	83	81	85	50	.41	81	85	50	.43
No	13	22	10	0		0	18	4		17	19	15	50		19	15	50	
Alcohol history																		
Yes	66	61	67	100	.51	100	67	63	.56	66	74	63	50	.55	75	65	50	.65

No	34	39	33	0		0	33	37		34	26	37	50		25	35	50	
Family History of Diabetes mellitus																		
Negative	15	96	84	0	.001	100	88	78	.41	11	89	88	100	.88	94	87	100	.67
Positive	85	4	16	100	*	0	12	22		89	3	12	0		6	13	0	
Pr=Poor; Av= Average; Gd=Good; P=P value; Chi Square Test, P < .05 is significant.																		

Table No. 4: Test-Retest Comparison of Attitude Scores of Study Participants at Two Time Points.

Variables	Intervention Group (N = 86)									Control Group (N = 84)								
	Test (response in %)	Re-test (response in %)				Test (response in %)	Re-test (response in %)											
		(%)	-ve	Neu	+ve		P	-ve	Neu	+ve	P	(%)	-ve	Neu	+ve	P	-ve	Neu
Age																		
<40 years	12	0	14	10	.74	0	13	0	.65	6	0	14	10	.21	7	5	6	.39
40-60 years	59	0	60	59		67	59	67		48	0	60	59		38	53	48	
>60 years	29	0	26	31		33	29	33		46	0	26	31		55	42	46	
Gender																		
Male	57	0	54	59	.68	0	67	56	.62	49	0	48	50	.89	0	45	52	.55
Female	43	0	46	41		0	33	44		51	0	52	50		0	55	48	
BMI																		
Under weight	1	0	0	2	.005*	0	0	1	.06	0	0	0	0	.90	0	0	0	.82
Ideal weight	37	0	15	52		0	0	40		35	0	32	37		0	31	37	
Over weight	53	0	73	40		0	67	52		59	0	61	58		0	62	58	
Obese	9	0	12	6		0	33	7		6	0	6	5		0	7	5	
Diet																		
Veg	9	0	3	14	.09	0	0	10	.42	3	0	5	0	.20	0	0	5	.22
Non-Veg	0	0	0	0		0	0	0		0	0	0	0		0	0	0	
Mixed Diet	91	0	97	86		0	100	90		97	100	95	0		0	100	95	
Occupation																		
Un employed	34	0	17	35	.32	0	17	35	.32	30	0	38	27	.25	38	27	30	.25
Self employed	54	0	83	53		0	83	53		65	0	62	67		62	67	65	
Employed	12	0	0	13		0	0	13		5	0	0	6		0	6	5	
Smoking history																		

Yes	87	0	83	90	.31	0	50	90	.005*	83	19	16	0	.65	0	14	18	.59
No	13	0	17	10		0	50	10		17	81	84	0		0	86	82	
Alcohol history																		
Yes	66	0	60	71	.31	0	50	68	.38	66	32	34	0	.83	0	31	35	.71
No	34	0	40	29		0	50	33		34	68	66	0		0	69	65	
Family History of Diabetes mellitus																		
Negative	15	0	97	76	.009*	0	100	84	.28	11	84	91	0	.29	0	79	93	.05
Positive	85	0	3	24		0	0	16		89	16	9	0		0	21	7	

-Ve=Negative attitude; Neu=Neutral attitude; +Ve=Positive attitude; *Chi Square Test, p < .05 is significant.

Table No. 5: Test-Retest Comparison of Practice based Score of study Participants at two time points.

Variables	Intervention Group (N = 86)									Control Group (N = 84)								
	(%)	Test (response in %)				Re-test (response in %)				(%)	Test (response in %)				Re-test (response in %)			
		Pr	Av	Gd	P	Pr	Av	Gd	P		Pr	Av	Gd	P	Pr	Av	Gd	P
Age																		
<40 yrs	12	12	14	11	.86	0	0	13	NC	6	6	7	7	.16	0	7	5	.62
40-60 yrs	59	59	55	61		0	67	59		48	48	54	54		0	38	53	
>60 yrs	29	29	32	28		0	33	29		46	46	39	39		0	55	42	
Gender																		
Male	57	41	63	0	.08	0	57	0	NC	49	67	0	0	.02*	62	44	0	.14
Female	43	59	38	0		0	43	0		51	33	0	0		38	56	0	
BMI																		
Under weight	1	0	2	0	.19	0	1	0	NC	0	0	0	0	.68	0	0	0	.88
Ideal weight	37	19	43	0		0	37	0		35	40	0	0		35	35	0	
Over weight	53	71	47	0		0	53	0		59	57	0	0		62	58	0	
Obese	9	10	8	0		0	9	0		6	3	0	0		4	6	0	
Diet																		
Veg	9	0	13	0	.08	0	9	0	NC	3	0	0	0	.21	0	5	0	.26
Non-Veg	0	0	0	0		0	0	0		0	0	0	0		0	0	0	
Mixed Diet	91	100	88	0		0	91	0		97	100	0	0		100	95	0	

Occupation																		
Unemployed	34	0	34	0	NC	50	35	30	NC	30	0	32	27	.34	44	28	0	.34
Self employed	54	0	55	0		50	53	59		65	0	62	73		56	68	50	
Employed	12	0	12	0		0	12	11		5	0	6	0		0	4	50	
Smoking history																		
Yes	87	86	88	0	.89	0	87	0	NC	83	70	0	0	.02*	77	86	0	.32
No	13	14	13	0		0	13	0		17	30	0	0			23	14	
Alcohol history																		
Yes	66	64	67	0	.76	0	66	0	NC	66	63	0	0	.67	69	65	0	.71
No	34	36	33	0		0	34	0		34	37	0	0			31	35	
Family History of Diabetes mellitus																		
Negative	15	95	81	0	.11	0	85	0	NC	11	93	0	0	.33	92	87	0	.49
Positive	85	5	19	0		0	15	0		89	7	0	0			8	13	

NC=Not Computed; Pr=Poor; Av= Average; Gd=Good; P=P value; Chi Square Test, p < .05 is significant.

DISCUSSION

Principal findings

The study assessed the influence of patient counseling on the diabetes control of (n=86) participants out of 175 total study participants. The comparison of the intervention (n=86) and control groups (n=89) revealed significant increases in medication adherence and KAP scores. Furthermore, the HbA1C levels in the intervention group were lower at post intervention, indicating better glycemic management. These findings coincide with earlier research demonstrating the potential favorable influence of patient education on diabetes outcomes.^[9,10] The study examined the KAP and medication adherence of patients with diabetes using standardized questionnaires. Good internal consistency was shown by significant Cronbach's alpha values upon validation of the adapted questionnaire. About 175 participants were involved in the study; 86 were in the intervention group and 89 were in the control group. There were slightly more male participation in the intervention group (57%), and most were in the 40–60 age range. The mean duration of diabetes in the intervention group was 5.9 years, while the control group's duration was 5.09 years. It was reported that 11% of the control group and 15% of the intervention group had a family history of diabetes.^[11] The intervention group dramatically improved their diabetic KAP and medication adherence by learning about type 1 and type 2 diabetes, detecting symptoms, and making lifestyle changes. They also had more positive attitudes regarding diabetes control, including improved awareness of exercise, medication adherence, and follow-up visits. However, medication adherence scores rose dramatically, emphasizing the relevance of patient counseling in improving treatment program adherence.^[12]

Following the counselling session, the knowledge questionnaire showed a considerable improvement, with a median score rising from 5 to 10 ($p < .001$) in the intervention group when compared to control group. These findings were supported by the earlier study reported by Zoungas *et al.*, 2014 and Krass *et al.*, 2015.^[11,12] Older participants (> 60 years) retained more knowledge than younger participants ($p < 0.05$). Positive attitudes regarding diabetes treatment significantly improved in the intervention group, and they became more aware of the importance of regular exercise, taking prescription drugs as directed, and turning toward follow-up appointments. The intervention group saw improvements in routine blood glucose tests, medical visits, and foot care. On the other hand, the intervention group's medication adherence scores also significantly improved, indicating the impact of patient counselling in improving treatment plan adherence.^[13,14] The study demonstrated a considerable

improvement in overall KAP scores after intervention. Participants with "poor" KAP scores fell from 26% at baseline test to 11% at post intervention re-test, while those with "good" scores rose from 29% to 61% ($p < .001$) respectively.

This represents that diabetes control habits were improved by the educational intervention. The intervention group's median medication adherence score increased from 29 to 35 ($p < .001$), indicating a substantial rise in medication adherence.^[15,16]

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the participant's capacity to manage their diabetes was significantly improved by educational intervention. The intervention group's scores on KAP and medication adherence all displayed substantial improvements. Patient education was successfully carried out by the potential clinical pharmacist (intern). The total KAP ratings following the session were greatly raised from poor to good, suggesting that intervention has increased participants' diabetes awareness and care. Healthcare institutions aiming to enhance the patient outcomes should consider introducing such initiatives.

Limitations

The study on DM discovered a gender imbalance of participants, using a larger male in the intervention group. This might add selection bias, limiting the generalizability of the findings. The prospective longitudinal interventional approach and self-reported data may potentially result in recollection bias. This investigation's concentration on diabetic individuals at a single private educational institution restricts its generalizability to other groups. The lack of cause-and-effect analysis, as well as the exclusion of comorbidities, might all be having an influence on the outcomes.

Recommendation

Systematic patient counselling programs greatly control hyperglycemia and should be a part of routine treatment regimens. These activities should close certain data shortages, encourage regular follow-ups, and customize treatments for high-risk populations. Technological advancements including mobile applications and telemedicine can improve patient care, while regulatory improvements enable login to standardized diabetic education. Healthcare practitioners should get training in effective communication and counseling.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ARB Angiotensin II receptor blocker BMI Body mass index

CCB Calcium channel blocker CCF Case Collection Form CI Confidence Interval

HbA1C Glycated Haemoglobin (Haemoglobin A1c) ICF Informed consent form

OPD Outpatient department T1DM Type 1 diabetes mellitus T2DM Type 2 diabetes mellitus

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